

Event metadata

Event title	What exactly is bioinformatics?
Event type	Webinar
Date of event	07/08/2024
Time of event	12pm AEST
Topic description	<p>‘Doing’ bioinformatics to extract, process, analyse, and interpret experimental results is something that all life scientists do as part of their research. But what exactly is bioinformatics? And is there a right (or a wrong) way to do it?</p> <p>In this webinar, Dr Georgie Samaha welcomes you to the vast world of bioinformatics.</p> <p>We explore common experimental use cases and share essential - but easy to overlook - practical tips for accessing data, software, and computing resources you need to get your research done.</p>
Format description	Webinar presentation followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/sih-what-is-bioinf
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	This webinar is for life scientists who are looking to get started or build their skills in bioinformatics.
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	<p>You will be able to answer key questions including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What does a typical experiment look like? • What kind of data will I work with? • What is involved in data-preprocessing?

	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• What's involved in data analysis?• Where can I do bioinformatics?
Speakers	Speaker: Dr Georgina Samaha, Bioinformatics Group Lead at Sydney Informatics Hub at the University of Sydney and Australian BioCommons Host: Dr Patrick Capon, Australian BioCommons
Related material	None